

A PROTOCOL FOR A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF EVIDENCE ON CONSUMER PREFERENCES AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY FOR INSECTS AS FOOD AND FEED INGREDIENT

Mariam Nikravech ^{1*}, Ana I. de Almeida Costa², Birgit A. Rumpold ¹, and Nina Langen¹

¹Department Education for Sustainable Nutrition and Food Science, Technical University Berlin, Berlin, Germany;

²Universidade Católica Portuguesa, Católica Lisbon School of Business & Economics Palma de Cima 1649-023 Lisboa, Portugal

Contact author: mariam.nikravech@tu-berlin.de

Abstract

This article presents a protocol for a systematic review of studies measuring consumer preferences and WTP for food made with edible insects, or food derived of animals fed with insects, employing preference elicitation methods. The goal of this study is to provide a summary of current consumers' preferences for food made with edible insects, or food derived of animals fed with insects. This protocol outlines the aims of the study, inclusion criteria and search and screening strategies, at title and abstract and full text level, the data extraction protocol and critical appraisal.

1. Background and aims of the study

In light of the emergence of the insect production sector in Europe and North-America, several reviews summarizing evidence on consumers' acceptance of insect-based foods have been published in recent years (Hartmann and Siegrist 2017; Kröger et al. 2022; Mancini et al. 2019; Sogari et al. 2019; Onwezen et al. 2021). These have comprehensively mapped the main factors influencing western consumers' acceptance for such products, namely sociodemographics, attitudes, food consumption habits, product attributes and sensory quality and contextual factors. However, and to the best of our knowledge, no systematic review has yet attempted to summarize evidence and provide estimates of different consumer segments' preference and Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) for insect-based foods. Given the growing evidence based on preference elicitation methods on consumer demand for insect-based food, it is relevant to provide a comprehensive synthesis of existing estimates. Moreover, extant reviews on insect-based food acceptance often do not provide a critical appraisal of existing evidence nor assess the quality of the studies generating it. Importantly, they also tend to be less comprehensive in regard to studies conducted in non-Western consumer markets as well as to experimental studies.

To narrow this knowledge gap, the goal of this review is to determine current consumer demand for food made with edible insects, or food derived of animals fed with insects, based on the findings of studies eliciting consumer preferences and WTP estimates in different geographical markets. This review will also cover sources of heterogeneity in consumer preferences, such as sociodemographics, attitudes, food consumption habits, among others studied so far, as well as the effects of interventions like the provision of information, participation in taste trials, pricing tactics or association with health claims.

Ultimately, this review seeks to provide market insights to insect-chain actors as well as important policy implications concerning the widening of acceptance of consumers for insect-based food and feed. Namely, it seeks to provide comprehensive evidence to inform market regulations on insect-based food and feed in adequation with the potential market, and the design of information campaigns to enhance the acceptability of insect-based food products and of certification patterns (e.g., nutritional claims, environmental, animal welfare, risk perception, food safety, allergies) that can help increase consumer acceptance for insects as food and feed ingredient for farm animals.

2. Review questions

This review seeks firstly to identify the effects of the incorporation of insects as ingredients directly in foods, or indirectly, in the feed of farm animals raised for food production on consumer preference and WTP estimates for derived products and their attributes, as reported in peer-reviewed studies employing standard preference elicitation methods. This will help identify the right product development strategies to increase demand, both based on intrinsic and extrinsic product characteristics. There is also a need to critically assess the methods used for evaluation of consumers acceptance for insect-based food products.

In addition, this review seeks to identify potential moderating effects of product characteristics, study design and modelling approaches on preference estimates for insect-based food products and meat of insect-fed animal.

Criteria for considering studies for the review

The PICO framework was employed to establish eligibility criteria and guide the search strategy.

1.1. Eligibility criteria

Publication type	English peer-reviewed articles and conference proceeding papers Empirical quantitative research papers
Date ranges	All up to April 2023
Study design	Stated and revealed preference elicitation methods. Studies that report estimates of preferences and/or WTP for product attributes and attributes levels. Revealed Preference measures: -Hedonic models -Real choice experiment -Auctions (BSM Lottery, bidding game) Stated preference measures: -Discrete choice experiment -Conjoint analysis (contingent rating or paired comparison) -Contingent valuation methods (Dichotomous choice, Payment card, Open-ended)
Population	Healthy adult humans, all gender identities, in all countries End-consumers only, i.e. individual not involved in the insect rearing, production and/processing activities (no producers, farmers, cook).
Primary Interventions	Insect-based food products, incl. edible insects, food product derived of insect-based ingredient, Insect-based feed, Food product of animal origin (including egg, meat, dairy), made of or from animal fed with insect, insect meal, insect-based feed All foods, beverages, food supplements and feeds are eligible as carrier for the incorporation of insects Offers at all stages of the product development and commercialization process – i.e., concepts, prototypes, market ready or commercial products – are eligible as stimuli to be evaluated
Secondary interventions	Product tastings, provision of information on public/private benefits or risks of integrating insects as feed or food ingredients, manipulation of retail environment, among others
Outcome of interest	Preference estimates per market and segment when available:

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilities for insect incorporation 2. Utilities for product attributes tied to insect incorporation (e.g., health claims) 3. Willingness-To-Pay (WTP)/marginal utilities for intervention products, their attributes and/or attribute levels
Settings	Real or hypothetical market conditions where at least visual or written information on insect integration (Y/N) and product prices or price ranges is available.

1.2. Search protocol

Search Methods	We conduct a text words search: we employ key words and natural language for each concept. Truncations and adjacencies are possible with the use of wildcards. All search strings are searched in the topic, keyword, title and abstracts filters of the databases with the help of Boolean operators AND and OR.
Search Strings (adapted to each database)	Search strings are organized along keywords for the following criteria: (1) Type of study/ (2) Intervention/ (3) Outcome. The core list of keywords is provided in annex. Search strings are adapted to each database, based on the core list of keywords.
Bibliographic databases	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Web of Sciences (Social Sciences Indexes used only) 2) ScienceDirect 3) JSTOR 4) Scopus 5) EBSCO Database: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Frontiers Journal Series (Open Access) b. IOP Journals c. SAGE Psychology d. SAGE Management and Organization Studies Collection e. Springer f. Emerald Journals g. PsycARTICLES 6) AgrEcon Search
Web-based databases	Google Scholar (first five pages)
Organizational websites	n/a
Other methods used for identifying relevant research	Snowballing techniques: the bibliography of all publications reviewed at full-text screening are searched Forward citations of all included studies.
Search updates	Update for literature published until May 2023

Screening strategy

All search results are stored in the reference management software Citavi, before screening. They are then imported into a systematic review management software, COVIDENCE, where they are systematically screened against the eligibility criteria following a two-step procedure, (a) a title and abstract screening and (b) a full text screening. Two members of the review team independently screen search results (a) and publications (b) for eligibility, while a third member resolves any conflicts emerging between them.

Removal of duplicates

Three measures were taken to remove duplicates: first, automatically, upon import of search results to CITAVI, then, and also automatically, upon import to COVIDENCE, and finally manually during the screening procedure.

We provide a PRISMA diagram to present the flow of the search, title and abstract screening, full text screening and tally included and excluded search results, publications and finally studies.

a- Title and Abstract screening

Screening begins based on pre-specified inclusion criteria. In total, two independent screeners review the abstracts and classify as “include”, “exclude” or “maybe”. Screeners are to remain inclusive, when uncertain.

Each abstract is screened by two screeners in COVIDENCE. In case of abstract classification conflicts between two screeners, a third reviewer (referee) resolves the conflict. In case an abstract is categorized “maybe” by at least one screener, the third reviewer resolves the conflict.

We report on the number of results excluded at title and abstract screening stage, based on COVIDENCE outputs.

b- Full text screening

Access to full-texts is though for each record retained after title and abstract screening. We get access using the following strategies:

- Download PDF from Open Access
- Email Authors via Research Gate
- Borrowing via University interlibrary loan
- Report document retrieval: Found/Not Found

Each full text retained after title and abstract screening is read and classified “exclude” or “include” by two independent reviewers, based on the exclusion criteria, incl. unavailability. In case of full text classification conflicts between two screeners, a third reviewer (referee) resolves the conflict.

Reports of reasons for exclusion is provided by COVIDENCE. A list of papers excluded at full text screening phase is provided as well as the reasons why they were considered to be ineligible for this review.

At that stage, individual papers are clustered within studies, if applicable.

We check consistency of the decision-making by providing the estimated proportion of articles/studies that received the same voting by the two reviewers.

Exclusion criteria

Not about insect-based food, feed, or meat of insect-fed animal
No elicitation of consumers preferences or WTP
Not revealed or stated preference elicitation methods
Information on product price or price range is not available

Data extraction strategy

Meta-data, data extraction and coding (Full text) strategy:

The extraction of metadata, study findings and their coding take place following several steps:

Step 1:

Citations of the included articles are exported from COVIDENCE into the literature management software Citavi. Full texts are stored and accessed in COVIDENCE for review and extraction of metadata.

Step 2:

Data and metadata are extracted using a COVIDENCE data extraction template. This form allows systematic extraction of study meta-data, study characteristics information and estimates for meta-analysis. Repeatability of the meta-data and data extraction process is ensured by the presence of a data extraction template. The data extraction template allows to collect a maximum of information relevant to the study questions based on selected variables. It also allows to input free texts and comments. It was tested by two reviewers and adapted to ensure it records all necessary information. It includes the following sections: General information, population, participants in study, methods, DCE products and attributes, Choice design, intervention group, outcomes, analysis and estimation results, applicability. The full list of variables used in the data extraction form are provided in annex.

Step 3:

We extract full study findings in COVIDENCE using the COVIDENCE data extraction template. Each study is read and extracted independently by two reviewers, and results are checked by a third one, to avoid bias and errors, and to solve any discrepancies. After this, extracted data is merged based the two independent extractions.

Data synthesis

The data synthesis will be both narrative and quantitative. We first present descriptive results about the study characteristics of the included studies: sample size, country of the study, year, and the choice design characteristics, insect species. These descriptive results will be summarized in an appendix.

In a second time, we present a quantitative synthesis analysis of the study findings. This quantitative synthesis allows to compile estimates in a subgroup analysis to account for heterogeneity across studies and to detect potential effect modifiers and reasons for heterogeneity. The quantitative synthesis strategy proposes to present mean preference and WTP estimates by subgroups, along the following sources of heterogeneity of preference estimates:

Study design (e.g. DCE, BWS) and modelling approaches (choice task design, incl. number of alternatives + presence of none option, type of choice (labelled/unlabeled), presence of visual cue, presence of treatment, presence of covariates in the models, experimental design if any), product characteristics (carrier product, insect-related attributes and attribute levels). Effect sizes and magnitudes will be compared along these groups to account for possible heterogeneity in study results. When not available, we compile adjusted WTP estimates in EUR using the delta method, with the help of the choice estimates in the preference space.

The present review will not include a meta-analysis in case the number of reviewed studies (less than ten) is estimated to be too low to ensure sufficient power.

In case a meta-analysis is possible to compile an overall effect, we will assess risk of publication bias by using an asymmetric funnel plot.

Procedural independence is ensured, as none of the systematic review researchers authored a study susceptible to be considered as part of this systematic review.

Critical appraisal strategy

A preliminary overview of literature showed that some of the studies potentially of interest to this review combine preference elicitation methods with experimental research designs (e.g., Lombardi et al., 2019; Alemu et al., 2020). In view of this, we employ two quality assessment tools to evaluate the methodological quality and the risk of bias of the studies reviewed. The first tool was developed by Clark et al (2017) for a non-healthcare context, grading specifically preference elicitation studies on three domains: (1) Design and application of the elicitation method; (2) Modelling of preference data; (3) Definition of population and sampling method. The second tool was developed by the Effective Public Health Practice Project (EPHPP) in Canada (Armijo-Olivo et al., 2012), grading quantitative studies in general on eight domains: (A) selection bias; (B) study design; (C) confounders; (D) blinding; (E) data collection method; (F) withdrawals/dropouts; (G) intervention integrity; and (H) analysis. Tools are combined when redundant and adapted where not applicable. Domains (A), (D), (E) and (H) of the EPHPP are dropped, whereas (B), (C), (F) and (G) are applied with some adjustments. All domains from Clarke et al. (2017) are applied with minor adjustments.

Two reviewers independently rate, per domain, the methodological quality of each study as “Poor”, “Average” or “Good” and after grade the risk of bias associated accordingly as: “High” (a grade of “Poor” in two or more quality criteria), “Moderate” (a grade of “Poor” in one quality criteria) or “Low” (Not graded “Poor”). Based on domain grades, they then independently grade the overall risk of bias as “High” (a “High” grade in two or more domains), “Moderate” (a “High” grade in one domain) or “Low” (No “High” grade). Whenever overall grades do not concur, reviewers revise each other’s domain grades and quality ratings to identify the reasons for discrepancy. There are then discussed (and with a third reviewer, if need be) to resolve discrepancies and produce a final, overall risk of bias grade per study. Both final (consensual) and intermediary (independent) assessments are reported.

Declarations of Competing Interest

The review authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Publication bibliography

Dalton, Jarrod E.; Bolen, Shari D.; Mascha, Edward J. (2016): Publication Bias: The Elephant in the Review. In *Anesthesia and analgesia* 123 (4), pp. 812–813. DOI: 10.1213/ANE.0000000000001596.

Hartmann, Christina; Siegrist, Michael (2017): Consumer perception and behaviour regarding sustainable protein consumption: A systematic review. In *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 61, pp. 11–25. DOI: 10.1016/j.tifs.2016.12.006.

Kröger, Tienieke; Dupont, Jacqueline; Büsing, Lucy; Fiebelkorn, Florian (2022): Acceptance of Insect-Based Food Products in Western Societies: A Systematic Review. In *Front. Nutr.* 8, Article 759885. DOI: 10.3389/fnut.2021.759885.

Mancini, Simone; Moruzzo, Roberta; Riccioli, Francesco; Paci, Gisella (2019): European consumers' readiness to adopt insects as food. A review. In *Food Research International* 122, pp. 661–678. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodres.2019.01.041.

Onwezen, M. C.; Bouwman, E. P.; Reinders, M. J.; Dagevos, H. (2021): A systematic review on consumer acceptance of alternative proteins: Pulses, algae, insects, plant-based meat alternatives, and cultured meat. In *Appetite* 159, p. 105058. DOI: 10.1016/j.appet.2020.105058.

Sogari, Giovanni; Menozzi, Davide; Hartmann, Christina; Mora, Cristina (2019): How to Measure Consumers Acceptance Towards Edible Insects? – A Scoping Review About Methodological Approaches. In Giovanni Sogari, Cristina Mora, Davide Menozzi (Eds.): *Edible Insects in the Food Sector: Methods, Current Applications and Perspectives*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 27–44. Available online at https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-22522-3_3.